

Mixed Dentition Space Analysis In Orthodontics: A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Space analysis plays a vital role in when mixed dentition is present in early diagnosis of orthodontic and planning of treatment by evaluating the relationship between unerupted permanent teeth size and available arch space. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the various space analysis techniques employed during the mixed dentition phase, encompassing both conventional and digital methodologies. A detailed classification framework is presented based on objectives, methodology, purpose, evaluated parameters, and the use of digital tools. Key predictive methods such as direct radiographic measurements, statistical prediction equations, and their combinations are discussed. Prominent techniques including the Probability Method of Moyers and analysis of Tanaka-Johnston are critically examined, with attention to their clinical applications and limitations. The influence of racial, ethnic, and gender variations on tooth size prediction is also addressed, alongside the impact of different predictor tooth selections on the accuracy of estimations. Furthermore, the integration of digital technologies in space analysis is explored, highlighting their potential to enhance diagnostic precision and efficiency in contemporary orthodontic practice.

Keywords - Mixed dentition, Prediction table, Space analysis

Introduction

A thorough diagnosis along with comprehensive planning of treatment are fundamental of an effective orthodontic care.¹ Among the diagnostic tools available, Study Model Analysis (SMA) holds a central role, particularly during the mixed dentition phase, by providing a three-dimensional evaluation of dental relationships and malocclusion patterns.² One of the most critical components of SMA is space analysis, which involves assessing arch length and tooth size discrepancy (TALD), tooth size prediction, and the proportional relationships between teeth - key factors that guide early orthodontic intervention.³

Space analysis in mixed dentition, helps clinicians to evaluate the size and orientation of unerupted permanent teeth in relation to the available space in arch. It is crucial for identifying potential crowding or spacing issues prior the permanent dentition eruption. By estimating future tooth positions and space requirements, orthodontists can make informed decisions regarding interceptive treatments such as space maintenance, expansion, interproximal reduction, or even extractions, if

necessary.

An effective space analysis in this stage aids in planning tooth movement while considering both functional and aesthetic goals. It allows for early correction of developing malocclusions and helps ensure proper alignment, overjet, and overbite relationships.⁴ Additionally, the analysis incorporates an understanding of individual anatomical variations, including arch length, tooth size, width, and skeletal growth patterns - factors that are particularly dynamic during the mixed dentition period.

Dental malocclusions during this stage often result from discrepancies between the size of erupting permanent teeth and available space in the dental arches. Addressing these discrepancies early supports better treatment outcomes and minimizes the need for more complex interventions later. A wide range of established techniques exists in the literature for analyzing space in the mixed dentition,

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including radiographic assessments, prediction equations, and digital methodologies. These tools serve as essential diagnostic aids, enabling orthodontists to evaluate developing occlusions, anticipate future dental alignment challenges, and craft individualized, growth-conscious treatment plans.

Space Analysis In Mixed Dentition

The phase of mixed dentition, occurring between six to twelve years, is crucial period in dental development, characterized by the simultaneous presence of both dentition that is deciduous and permanent. In this transitional period, orthodontists can effectively predict future dental change and assess the likelihood of spacing or crowding issues within the dental arch.⁵ Mixed Dentition Space Analysis is technique used by orthodontists to check the space necessary for permanent teeth which is unerupted before their emergence in the dental arch.⁶ In space analysis of mixed dentition, predicting the width of unerupted permanent premolars and canines mesiodistally stands as a key component in evaluating dental arch space and planning for optimal tooth alignment. The process of mesiodistal width prediction of unerupted canines and premolars involves various methods, including dental models, radiographic analysis, and clinical examination.

1. Direct Radiographic Measurement

The permanent premolars and canines (both first and second) width from dental radiographsis directly measured, including cephalometric and periapical images.^{7,8} Numerous studies have proposed techniques to enhance the precision of estimating the size of unerupted teeth through the utilization of dental radiographs.

2. Use Equation of Prediction and/ or Table

These methods estimate the size of unerupted premolars and canines based on the known widths of erupted teeth, typically the mandibular incisors.^{9,10} Among the most frequently utilized methods are probability tables of Moyer's and the equations of regression developed by Tanaka and Johnston.

a. Moyers Probability Analysis

One of the most widely used non-radiographic techniques, this method utilizes probability charts developed from a large population database. By measuring the addition of the mandibular four incisors, clinicians can estimate the mesiodistal widths of the unerupted premolars and canines with a chosen level of statistical confidence (e.g., 75%, 85%).¹⁰

This method is widely preferred for mixed dentition due to several advantages:

1. It exhibits less known systematic error.
2. Can be utilized by both novices and experts with equal reliability.
3. Less consumption of time.
4. It does not necessitate any special equipment and/or radiographic exposure.
5. It is applicable in lower and upper dental arches both.
6. While ideally done on casts, it can be reasonably performed in the mouth.

Method of Moyer's is frequently applied by numerous populations.^{11,12} Ackerman and Profit also found the Moyers method relevant¹³

b. Method of Tanaka and Johnston

It is used to predict the size of unerupted premolars and canines without the need for radiographs. It helps orthodontists in planning space management, extractions, or other treatments.

Key Feature : The method relies on the addition of the mesiodistal widths of the four permanent incisors of mandibular, which are two central incisors and two lateral incisors. These teeth erupt early and are easy to measure clinically.⁹

The Prediction Equations : Once you measure the width of the four mandibular incisors, you apply the following equations:

For Mandibular Arch (Each Quadrant):

Predicted width of one mandibular canine + premolars = (total of mandibular incisors ÷ 2) + 10.5 mm

For Maxillary Arch (Each Quadrant)

Predicted width of one maxillary canine + premolars = (total of mandibular incisors ÷ 2) + 11.0 mm So, if the total of the four mandibular incisors is 24 mm:

Predicted width for one side in the lower jaw = (24 ÷ 2) + 10.5 = 22.5 mm

Predicted width for one side in the upper jaw = (24 ÷ 2) + 11.0 = 23.0 mm

To get the total for both quadrants (right and left), just multiply by 2:

Mandible total : 22.5 mm × 2 = 45.0 mm

Maxilla total : 23.0 mm × 2 = 46.0 mm

Advantages : Simple and quick: Only a caliper and a calculator are needed.

Non-invasive : No radiographs required.

Reasonably accurate for most patients.

Applicable to both males and females, and to both dental arches.

Limitations : May not be accurate in cases of ethnic variation, tooth size anomalies, or dental crowding.

It is a statistical estimation and not a precise prediction.

Accuracy may be lower in populations different from the one it was originally developed on (Caucasian children in the U.S.).

3. Combination of Radiographic measurement and Prediction Equation

This method is a more advanced and often more accurate technique for predicting the mesiodistal width (side-to-side width) of unerupted premolars and canines, especially compared with purely clinical or non-radiographic approaches (like Tanaka and Johnston).

This Method Combines Direct measurement from dental radiographs (X-rays) – specifically the first and second premolars that may be visible but not erupted. And clinical measurement of erupted mandibular incisors (central + lateral) – just like in simpler methods. Together, these measurements are used in a regression equation to estimate the full size of the premolars and canines.^{7,14-16}

Historical Development of This Method

a. Hixon and Oldfather (1958)

They were the first to suggest using radiographic measurements to estimate the size of unerupted mandibular canines and premolars. They created regression equations – mathematical formulas based on observed data to make these predictions.¹⁶

a. Stahle (1959)

He improved the method by adding the size of the mandibular incisors (central and lateral). This addition made the prediction more accurate.¹⁷

b. Staley and Kerber (1980)

They refined the method further and developed better prediction equations. Also, they Created graphs to help estimate the mesiodistal widths more visually and easily. Their version is considered a more clinically practical tool and is commonly referenced.¹⁸

Prediction Equation or Table Vs Radiographic

In orthodontics, there are main two approaches to predict the unerupted teeth size (especially premolars and canines):

a. Radiographic Prediction Method

PROS : Uses X-rays to directly measure the unerupted teeth size and can give individual specific information if done correctly.

CONS : Requires high-quality radiographic equipment and technique because poor X-rays can lead to inaccurate measurements. Also, radiographs are 2D, but teeth are 3D so if a tooth is rotated inside the bone (before eruption), its width can appear smaller or larger than it actually is.¹⁹

Radiation exposure is involved, which is a concern especially in children.

Radiographs can be accurate but are dependent on technique and equipment, and they carry some health risks.

B. Prediction Equations And Tables (non-radiographic Methods):

Instead of using X-rays, these methods estimate the size of unerupted teeth depend on already erupted teeth size -usually the mandibular incisors. Common Method used is Moyer's Probability Tables which uses statistical tables based on population data and gives a predicted range (with certain probabilities, e.g., 75% or 85% confidence).⁷⁻¹⁰

Ethnic and Racial Difference in Tooth Size

Studies have shown that tooth size differ among different ethnic and racial groups. These variations are influenced by a mix of genetic factors (inherited traits), epigenetic factors (how genes are expressed, which can be affected by things like nutrition or health) and environmental factors (such as diet, climate, or cultural habits).^{20,21}

Many of the commonly used tooth size prediction methods like:

Moyer's Probability Tables

Tanaka and Johnston's Regression Equations

Which were developed based on studies done in North American Caucasian children. As a result, these methods are tailored to average tooth sizes and patterns found in that specific

group. They not always accurate when applied to children from different ethnic or racial backgrounds, such as African, Asian, Hispanic, Indigenous populations.

Difference of Gender in Tooth Size

Although commonly used tooth size prediction methods - such as those by Moyer and Tanaka & Johnston - have been widely applied in clinical settings, they were not originally designed to differentiate between males and females. This is a significant limitation because numerous studies have consistently shown that size of tooth varies by gender, in which males generally have bigger teeth than females, especially in terms of width mesiodistally (the width of the tooth from front to back along the dental arch).²² This biological difference, known as sexual dimorphism, is particularly important when predicting the size of unerupted per-manent premolars and canines in planning of orthodontic treatment.

Due to this well-documented variation, many researchers argue that gender should be considered as a key factor in tooth size prediction. Ignoring gender can lead to inaccurate estimations over estimating sizes in females or underestimating them in males which may result in inappropriate clinical decisions. Therefore, it is recommended that separate prediction tables and regression equations be developed for females and male.^{22,23} This would enhance the precision of mixed dentition analyses and lead to better orthodontic outcomes by accounting for the natural variation in tooth size between the genders.

1. Mixture of Group of Teeth Used as Predictor

In orthodontics, predicting the size of unerupted permanent canines and premolars during the mixed dentition stage is essential for planning treatments like braces or extractions. To do this, researchers and clinicians use the mesiodistal widths (the front-to-back width along the arch) of already erupted teeth as predictors.

a. Traditional Predictor: addition of Four Incisors of Mandible

The most commonly used predictor is the combined width of the four permanent incisors of mandible. This method has been accepted widely and used in developing regression equations for estimating the size of unerupted premolars and canines across various populations.

Many researchers have supported this approach because these teeth erupt early and are easy to measure and they show a fairly consistent size pattern within populations. However, recent studies suggest that relying solely on these four incisors might not always provide the most accurate predictions, especially across diverse ethnic groups.^{19,24,25}

b. Alternative and Combined Predictors

To improve accuracy, researchers have explored other combinations of erupted teeth - beyond just the four mandibular incisors - as predictors. These combinations often include molars or maxillary incisors, based on population-specific characteristics.

For examples : In Brazilian population, the best predictor was found to be the total of permanent incisors of mandible and first molar of mandible. This combination gave better estimates of unerupted canine and premolar sizes.²⁶

In Spanish and Egyptian populations, the most accurate predictor was the combined width of the central incisor of maxilla and mandibular first molar. This combination worked better than using mandibular incisors alone.²⁷

In Peruvian population (Bernabé and Flores-Mir, 2005) A more accurate prediction was achieved using the addition of central incisors of maxillary and mandibular plus the maxillary first molar.²⁸

In Syrian, Croatian, and Italian populations the mixture of incisors of mandible and maxillary first molar was found the most reliable predictor. This combination has been supported by multiple studies in these regions.²⁹⁻³¹

Mixed Dentition Space Analysis Using Digital Models

In orthodontics space analysis in mixed dentition is done commonly using conventional plaster models. Digital models which are created with the help of intraoral scanner are not widely used in clinical setting. Okamoto et al. in his preliminary study evaluated that how well digital models can perform in the mixed dentition analysis compared to conventional plaster models.³² They measured the space which is needed for permanent premolars and canines teeth and also, they measured the arch length discrepancy.

Figure.1 : (a) Plaster model is made from an impression of the reference model using alginate impression material. (b) Digital model is obtained from an optical impression of the reference model using an intraoral scanner.

(Picture courtesy : Okamoto A, Karibe H, Tanaka S, Kawakami T, Shinya A. Reliability of mixed dentition space analysis using a digital model obtained from an optical impression: a preliminary study. *BMC Res Notes*. 2024 Jan 3;17(1):12)

The biggest difference among the digital and plaster model results was in the right side arch length discrepancy: Digital vs plaster showed a difference of -0.49 mm. However, this difference is very small and considered not significant clinically (in real practice, such a small difference wouldn't affect treatment decisions). Hence, concluded that the digital models are just as accurate as traditional plaster models for mixed dentition space analysis.³²

Conclusion

Space analysis during the mixed dentition phase is a cornerstone of early diagnosis of orthodontic and planning of treatment. Accurately predicting the mesiodistal width of unerupted permanent canines and premolars is essential to anticipate and manage potential space discrepancies in the dental arch. Various techniques - ranging from direct radiographic measurements to statistical prediction equations and their combinations - offer clinicians valuable tools for evaluating developing dentition. While widely used methods like Probability Tables of Moyer's and the equations of Tanaka-Johnston remain clinically relevant

due to their simplicity and non-invasive nature

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